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Citation: Naseem Fatima, Naseem A., Afzal A. 2025. Effect of Melatonin on Growth Performance, Gonadosomatic Index, and Hematological Profile of Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). 2(3), pp.34-39. <https://psn.ijfas.co/AE014137>

Introduction

Aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing food production sectors globally and plays a vital role in food security,

livelihoods and economic development (Wang et al., 2021). Among cultured species, Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) is very important because of its fast growth, adaptability to various environmental conditions, and

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. **FUNDING** The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

Research Article

Effect of Melatonin on Growth Performance, Gonadosomatic Index, and Hematological Profile of Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

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PSN: <https://psn.ijfas.co/AE014137>

Article History: Received 03/06/2025; Accepted 15/11/2025; Published 21/12/2025

Abstract

The accelerated growth of aquaculture requires development of effective strategies for collaborating the reproduction and increasing growth performance of commercially important fish species. This study examined the effect of dietary melatonin supplementation on growth, reproductive and hematological characteristics of *Oreochromis niloticus*. A total of 300 fish were split into control and experimental groups that were fed for 90 days a basal diet or with melatonin-enriched feed formulated with rice protein. Results showed significant decreases in body weight ($p = 0.016$), number of eggs ($p = 0.01$), gonadosomatic index (GSI) ($p = 0.02$) and hemoglobin concentration ($p = 0.028$) of melatonin-fed fish, but no significant effect on total length ($p = 0.20$). Correlation analysis indicated high positive correlation between GSI, hemoglobin and spawning frequency suggesting the coordinated suppression of reproduction and physiology. These results indicated that melatonin in the diet has a powerful role in controlling reproduction and metabolism in Nile tilapia. Future research should focus on the optimal dose and time to maximize broodstock management with minimum negative effects on somatic growth to increase sustainability of aquaculture.

Keywords

Nile tilapia, Melatonin, Gonadosomatic index, Hemoglobin, Spawning control

acceptance by the consumer. However, tilapia kept under intensive culture systems are subsequently exposed to stressors such as overcrowding and poor water quality which have a negative impact on growth, reproductive performance, and overall health. Consequently, finding low-cost and sustainable methods to improve tilapia aquaculture production and resistance capabilities continues to be one of the significant hurdles for the farming industry (Xiong et al., 2023).

Figure 1: Graphical Abstract.

Melatonin (N-acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine) is a neurohormone at the core of circadian and seasonal rhythms secreted from the pituitary gland that mainly regulates circadian rhythms, and plays a role in the control of growth, metabolism and reproduction in vertebrates (Shao and He, 2023). It has been known as an important regulator involved in photoperiodic regulation of fish reproduction, including the development of their gonads and spawning (Kim et al., 2018; Imamura et al., 2022). Recent research has added to the list of its known functions; including antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and growth-promoting characteristics (Falcon et al., 2010; Acharyya et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2024).

The effects of melatonin on fish reproduction seem to be species and dose dependent. Singh et al. (2011) reported the decline in gonadosomatic index (GSI) after exogenous melatonin treatment in Nile tilapia; while Samal et al. (2025) reported no significant somatic differences in response to supplementation of dietary. Similarly, Imamura et al (2023) showed that melatonin inhibited the development of ovaries in damsselfish, while a positive correlation between testicular melatonin and sperm

maturation was seen in endogynes by Acharyya and Hasan (2024). These variations imply that melatonin can have a dual reproductive function depending on environmental as well as physiological conditions.

Not only reproduction, there are also influences in this process on somatic growth and systemic physiology mediated by melatonin While Gupta et al. (2020) found growth suppression in tilapia exposed to melatonin, Veisi et al. (2021) found enhanced antioxidant capacity with no significant growth effects. Such discrepancies are probably due to differences in experimental design, photoperiod and dosage. Moreover, there is a lack of knowledge on hematological parameters, which are important indicative parameters of fish health and fish stress physiology, which limit the knowledge on the systemic implications of melatonin in tilapia.

Overall the literature is a complex picture of the role of melatonin in tilapia biology with contradictory reports on its influence on growth, reproduction and physiology. These inconsistencies are likely caused by differences in experimental conditions, mode of administration and species response.

Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the effects of dietary melatonin supplementation on growth performance, reproductive indices and hematological parameters in *Oreochromis niloticus*. The objective is therefore to clarify the melatonin integrative physiological role and its potential use in the improvement of aquaculture productivity and sustainability.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

1. The study was performed in Government Sadiq College Women University Bahawalpur which is situated at 29.3885 degrees north latitude and 71.7016 degrees east. A total of three hundred healthy Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) were used for experimentation, having the average initial weight was 70 g and total length was 8±0.5 cm. Fish were acclimatized during two weeks in 300 L glass aquaria with controlled 12 h light:12 h darkness photoperiod. During the acclimation period, fish were fed with a commercial diet with 32% crude protein and natural collected plankton to accelerate normal growth and gonadal development in the fish. After acclimation, fish were randomly allocated to two groups: a control

group and an experimental group that was melatonin treated. Mixing and preparation of melatonin diet method is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Stepwise preparation of melatonin infused feed for *Oreochromis niloticus*

Feed Formulation

The experimental diet was made using melatonin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) and rice protein as blend with base of ground feed pellets. Additional ingredients were refined wheat flour, sugar, 10g, salt, 10g, and baking yeast, 20g. All ingredients were mixed to make a uniform dough by homogenization with water, which was spread on glass trays and dried in a vacuum oven at 150deg C. The dried pellets were kept in air tight polyethylene bags. Fish were fed at body weight proportional to body weight, twice a day at 10:00 a.m. and 2:00 p.m. for a continuous period of three months Chen, Jinglong, et al.(2025).

Table 1: Composition of experimental feed used for *Oreochromis niloticus*.

Ingredient	Quantity per kg of feed (g)	Function
Ground feed pellets	600	Base feed providing protein and energy
Rice protein	200	Supplemental protein source
Melatonin	0.5	Neuroendocrine modulator to regulate reproduction

Refined wheat flour	100	Binder for pellet formation
Sugar	10	Energy source and palatability enhancer
Salt	10	Electrolyte balance and osmoregulation
Baking yeast	20	Vitamin source and fermentation aid
Water	60 mL	For dough homogenization
Total	1000 g	

Melatonin dose was 0.5 g/kg of feed. All values are given per 1 kg of feed. Water was added for dough homogenization, and the total feed weight equals 1 kg.

Environmental Conditions

Water quality parameters were recorded carefully so that the culture conditions were optimum. Temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen (DO) were kept at 25.5±2deg C, 7.2±0.1, and between 4.8–5.2 mg per liter respectively, Abd El-Hack, Mohamed E., et al.,(2022). These parameters were monitored periodically in order to minimize stress and achieve consistency in the environment over the course of the experiment.

Growth and Reproductive Assessment

Fish were pre handled with 50 parts per million (ppm) benzocaine to anesthetize them to reduce stress. Body weight and total length was measured every 30 days using a digital balance and Vernier caliper. Specific growth rate (SGR) and condition factor (K) were determined by use of conventional formulas. Female spawning activity was monitored daily during feeding and eggs were collected manually from the mouths of brooding females and counted. The gonadosomatic index (GSI) was determined at the end of the experiment with the use of the formula Kaur, S., Singh, P., & Hassan, S. S. (2018)

$$GSI = (\text{Body Weight} / \text{Gonad Weight}) \times 100$$

For males the testes were excised for determination of sperm count, spermatozoa index (SI) and spermatocrit. Sperm motility and sperm count were determined under the microscope using a hemocytometer after staining with 0.5% eosin solution in 1:10 dilution.

At the end of the trial, blood samples were withdrawn from the caudal vein by using 20-gauge needles and 10 mL syringes. Samples were collected into ethylene di

amine tetraacetic acid (EDTA)-coated vials and then stored at 4 degC until they were analyzed Duran, U., Çenesiz, S., & Şahin, B. (2023). Hemoglobin (Hb) concentration was determined using Symex KX-21 hematology analyzer.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed with the use of sheets of the statistical program, SPSS (version 26.0). Growth parameters that is weight and length, were analysed using linear mixed models with treatment and time as fixed factors and tank as a random factor to account for replication. GSI and Hb were analyzed with two-way ANOVA Al-Deghayem, Waleed A., et al(2017). The spawning frequency was modelled using generalized linear mixed models assuming negative binomial distributions. Any significant differences were further investigated using Tukey HSD post hoc test Mahalder, Balam, et al.(2025). Effect sizes, Confidence intervals (CI) and p values were included for all analyses. Statistical significance level was p less than 0.05.

Results

Somatic Growth Performance Dietary supplementation with melatonin had a noticeable effect on somatic growth of *O. niloticus*. The mean body weight of the experimental group (134.40 ± 57.76 g) was significantly less than the control group ($p=0.016$), indicating that the melatonin depressed somatic growth. By contrast, there was no significant difference in the mean total length of evidence on the treatments. These results indicate that melatonin seems to work mainly by decreasing the body mass accumulation instead of linear skeletal growth during experimental period.

Table 2: Growth, reproductive, and hematological parameters of *Oreochromis niloticus* fed control and melatonin-supplemented diets

Parameter	Control Group (Mean \pm SD)	Melatonin Group (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Body weight (g)	168.50 \pm 61.32	134.40 \pm 57.76	0.016*
Total length (cm)	17.85 \pm 3.12	17.32 \pm 3.04	0.200
Egg number	515.60 \pm 172.80	358.40 \pm 149.50	0.010*
GSI (%)	9.02 \pm 2.18	6.41 \pm 2.24	0.020*
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	11.42 \pm 2.74	9.19 \pm 2.60	0.028*

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Asterisks (*) mean significant differences to control and melatonin treated group ($p < 0.05$). Melatonin supplementation led to significant decline in body weight, number of eggs, gonadosomatic index (GSI), hemoglobin concentration, however, total length was not significantly different between treatments

Female Reproductive Parameters Reproductive activity was significantly inhibited by supplementation of melatonin feed in females. No spawning occurred in the first month of the trial and spawning resumed after about 60 days. The number of spawned eggs were significantly less in experimental (358.40 ± 149.50 ; $P = 0.01$) compared to control. Similarly, the gonadosomatic index (GSI) was much lower in melatonin treated females (6.41 ± 2.24 ; $p=0.02$). These results suggest that melatonin affects on gonadal maturation and ovulatory cycles, probably by endocrine modulation. As shown in Table 1, dietary melatonin had a significant negative effect on body weight, reproductive output (egg number and GSI) and a significant negative effect on hemoglobin compared to the control group.

Figure 3: Correlation heatmap of growth, reproductive, and hematological parameters in *O. niloticus*. Positive correlations (red) mean parameters that increase or decrease at the same time, and negative (blue) is the opposite, inverse relationship. Strong positive associations were observed between gonadosomatic index (GSI), hemoglobin (Hb) and spawning frequency suggesting that suppression by melatonin occurred simultaneously for these characters. Weak correlations between weight and other variables indicate that somatic growth was influenced independent of reproductive inhibition.

Male Reproductive Parameters Male reproductive performance was, however, affected by melatonin administration as well. Fish fed melatonin-enriched diet showed a decrease in the number of spermatozoa,

spermatozoa index (SI) and spermatocrit. Sperm motility was also decreased, which is indicative of delayed sexual maturation. These effects support the hypothesis that melatonin plays an important role in reproductive physiology as a way to decrease gonadotropin release and testicular responsiveness by the hypothalamus-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis.

Hematological Profile Melatonin treatment significantly altered the hematological parameters. Therefore, hemoglobin (Hb) concentration in the current group (9.19 ± 2.60 g/dL) was significantly lower than in the control group ($p = 0.028$), which reflects a physiological response to hormonal and environmental stress. Reduced Hb levels may indicate melatonin's effect on erythropoiesis or regulation of oxygen transport where melatonin is known for its role mediating metabolic and stress related pathways in fish. Correlation analysis (Figure 3) showed that there were strong positive relationships amongst GSI, Hb and spawning frequency, providing evidence for the coordinated inhibitory influence of melatonin on reproduction and physiology.

Discussion

The finding of inhibition in somatic growth is consistent with past studies showing melatonin's effect is species-dependent. While melatonin improved the growth in Atlantic salmon, it had neutral or negative impacts on the growth of *O. niloticus* and Masu salmon (Singh et al., 2011; Gupta et al., 2020). The present findings confirm melatonin suppresses growth in Nile tilapia, possibly by modulating metabolism and deciding allocation of energy rapidly by way of maintenance and endocrinal matter, moderately than deposit of tissue.

The effect of melatonin on reproduction strongly suppresses growth in both sexes is consistent with its known status as a photoperiodic regulator. In females lowering the spawning frequency and the number of eggs, and decreasing GSI values suggest gonadotropic activity inhibiting, while in males, reduction of the sperm indexes suggests delayed maturation of the testis. The down regulation of the HPG axis via melatonin may suppress the release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) which impairs gametogenesis.

Hematological changes also suggest the presence of a systemic effect of melatonin. The reduction in Hb concentration reflects physiological stress adaptation of melatonin according to its antioxidant and endocrine modulating activities. Together, these findings suggest that exogenous melatonin when fed as a part of diet is a

strong regulator of reproductive cycles and stress physiology in *O. niloticus*.

While the possible role of melatonin in the control of asynchronous spawning and the redirection of energy to somatic maintenance may be of interest. But the inhibitory implication of melatonin on growth performance needs to be carefully considered in aquaculture applications. Optimization of dosage, duration and environmental conditions is therefore essential before large scale implementation.

Conclusion

This study shows that supplementing the diet with melatonin is an effective way to regulate sexual activity of *Oreochromis niloticus* reproduction by suppressing spawning behaviour, gonadal development and sperm production in both sexes. The observed decrease in body mass and hemoglobin concentration is another sign that melatonin is altering the overall physiology, occurring as a trade of between body somatogenesis and reproductive regulation. These results give new importance to the use of melatonin as a neuroendocrine tool in the management of broodstock and precocious maturation of aquaculture systems. However, its application needs to be carefully optimized to balance the growth performance and inhibition of reproduction. The results have formed a basic basis of knowledge to develop hormonal management strategies to improve the productivity and sustainability of tilapia farming.

Acknowledgements

The researchers acknowledged the support given by the Virtual University of Pakistan and the *Government Sadiq College Women University, Bahawalpur*.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

References

- Acharyya, A., Das, J., & Hasan, K. N. (2024). Melatonin as a potential remedy in fish reproduction against environmental pollution: An emerging issue. In *Spatial Modeling of Environmental Pollution and Ecological Risk* (pp. 423-447). Woodhead Publishing.
- Chen, J., Du, Y., Zhang, M., Wang, J., Ming, J., Shao, X., ... & Liu, B. (2025). Effects of Melatonin on

- the Growth and Diurnal Variation of Non-Specific Immunity, Antioxidant Capacity, Digestive Enzyme Activity, and Circadian Clock-Related Gene Expression in Crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*). *Fishes*, 10(3), 114.
- Dominguez, M., Takemura, A., & Tsuchiya, M. (2005). Effects of changes in environmental factors on the non-specific immune response of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* L. *Aquaculture Research*, 36(4), 391-397.
- Gupta, G., Srivastava, P. P., Kumar, M., Varghese, T., Chanu, T. I., Gupta, S., & Ande, M. P. (2025). Effect of melatonin supplementation on gonadotropins, Vitellogenin gene expression, antioxidant status, ovarian histology and reproductive performance in female *Clarias magur*.
- Imamura, S., Hur, S. P., Takeuchi, Y., Badruzzaman, M., Mahardini, A., Rizky, D., & Takemura, A. (2022). Effect of short-and long-term melatonin treatments on the reproductive activity of the tropical damselfish *Chrysiptera cyanea*. *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, 48(1), 253-262.
- Kaur, S., Singh, P., & Hassan, S. S. (2018). Studies on Gonado-somatic index (GSI) of selected fishes of River Sutlej, Punjab. *Journal of Entomology sand Zoology Studies*, 6(2), 1274-1279.
- Kim, J. H., Park, J. W., Jin, Y. H., Kim, D. J., & Kwon, J. Y. (2018). Effect of melatonin on GnIH precursor gene expression in Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*. *Biological Rhythm Research*, 49(2), 303-313.
- Samal, K., Biswas, P., Singh, S. K., Das, P., Debbarma, R., Deb, S., ... & Borah, S. (2025). Dietary Melatonin Boosts Reproduction and Growth Performance of Ornamental Fish Giant Danio (*Devario aequipinnatus*): A Transformative Approach for Scrapping Wild-Caught Fish Business. *Aquaculture Nutrition*, 2025(1), 5540109.
- Shao, R., Wang, Y., He, C., & Chen, L. (2024). Melatonin and its emerging physiological role in reproduction: A review and update. *Current Molecular Medicine*, 24(4), 449-456.
- Singh, R., Singh, A. K., & Tripathi, M. (2012). Melatonin induced changes in specific growth rate, gonadal maturity, lipid and protein production in Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus 1758). *Asian-Australasian journal of animal sciences*, 25(1), 37.
- Wang, C., Li, Z., Wang, T., Xu, X., Zhang, X., & Li, D. (2021). Intelligent fish farm—the future of aquaculture. *Aquaculture International*, 29(6), 2681-2711.
- Xiong, W., Guo, C., Gozlan, R. E., & Liu, J. (2023). Tilapia introduction in China: Economic boom in aquaculture versus ecological threats to ecosystems. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 15(1), 179-197
- Zhao, R., Bai, Y., & Yang, F. (2024). Melatonin in animal husbandry: Functions and applications. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 11, 1444578.